

A COMPARATIVE STUDY OF ENGLISH AND UZBEK TERMS RELATING TO TAILOR

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Annotation: The main topic of this article is the comparative study of terminology related to craftsmanship in English and Uzbek languages. The aim is to assess the linguistic differences between the two languages and find anomalies in their terminology. The results of the research show that although Uzbek terminology is adapted to regional conditions and traditional customs, English expressions are more general in nature. Linguists, translators, and technical experts will find this page useful in understanding the differences in the origin and usage of cultural and technical terms.

Key words: tailor, semantic, terms, professional terms, industry, embroidery, stitch, sewing machine.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolaning asosiy mavzusi tikuvchilikka bilan bog‘liq terminologiyani ingliz va o‘zbek tillarida taqqoslashdir. Maqsad — ushbu ikki til orasidagi lingvistik farqlarni o‘rganish va terminologiyadagi nomuvofiqliklarni aniqlashdir. Tadqiqot natijalari shuni ko‘rsatadiki, o‘zbek terminologiyasi mintaqaviy sharoitlar va an‘anaviy urf-odatlariga moslashtirilgan bo‘lsa-da, inglizcha iboralar umumiyroq xususiyatga ega. Ushbu maqola lingvistlar, tarjimonlar va texnik mutaxassislar uchun madaniy va texnik atamalarining kelib chiqishi hamda ulardan foydalanishdagi farqlarni tushunishda foydalidir.

Kalit so‘zlar: tikuvchi, semantik, atamalar, kasbiy atamalar, sanoat, kashtachilik, chok, tikuv mashinasi.

Аннотация: Основная тема данной статьи — сравнительное изучение терминологии, связанной с швея, в английском и узбекском языках. Цель заключается в оценке языковых различий между этими двумя языками и выявлении аномалий в их терминологии. Результаты исследования показывают, что узбекская терминология адаптирована к региональным условиям и традиционным обычаям, тогда как английские выражения имеют более общий характер. Эта статья будет полезна лингвистам, переводчикам и техническим специалистам для понимания различий в происхождении и использовании культурных и технических терминов.

Ключевые слова: швея, семантика, термины, профессиональные термины, промышленность, вышивка, шов, швейная машина.

Introduction: The skill and quality of creating something by hand or with meticulous, professional craftsmanship is called artisanry. It often involves a

commitment to producing high-quality products using traditional methods. Sometimes referred to as craftsmanship, it is applied in various fields such as jewelry-making, pottery, textiles, tailoring, metalworking, woodworking, and handmade embroidery. The main characteristics of craftsmanship include:

1. **Skill and Experience:** The foundation of craftsmanship is knowledge and skill, which is frequently acquired through years of practice or handed down through generations.

2. **High-quality Materials:** To guarantee the longevity and beauty of their creations, craftsmen typically utilize natural, high-quality materials.

3. **Attention to Detail:** A skilled artisan takes the time to guarantee that each component of their work is completed precisely and carefully.

4. **Tradition and Innovation:** Although traditional methods are generally linked with craftsmanship, many craftspeople combine age-old methods with cutting-edge inventions.

In areas with rich artisanal traditions, craftsmanship is especially important for maintaining cultural heritage. In today's fast-paced world, it is also becoming more and more valued as consumers choose handmade, one-of-a-kind products over mass-produced ones.

Language plays a crucial role in professional domains, such as craft, and is an essential component of culture. The craftsmanship makes use of a wide range of professional and technical phrases that are derived from each language's cultural and technological development. The Uzbek terminology is based on the experience of local handicraft, whereas the English word represents global approaches. The terms used to describe workmanship in Uzbekistan and the United Kingdom are compared and contrasted in this article. The following are the research questions: What are the linguistic and semantic features of the terms related to craftsmanship in Uzbek and English?

In what social and cultural context are these terms used in both languages? What terms are compatible with each other in the Uzbek and English languages, and what terms have their own national characteristics?

Methodology:

The comparative linguistic analysis method was used to perform the research. To analyze the terminology of craftsmanship, historical materials such as technical books and textbooks, opportunities, sources, and contemporary writings were examined, along with specialized dictionaries available in both English and Uzbek. The research methodology used in this study was comparative analysis. The English and Uzbek dictionary of craftsmanship is derived from special dictionaries, technical documents and information collected by experts in the field. The terms were examined taking into account the grammatical, lexical and semantic features of the two languages. The cultural origin and etymology of these expressions are also taken into account. The goal is to find similarities and differences between each term in Uzbek and English.

Results:

The study's findings demonstrate that English terms associated with craftsmanship are more closely tied to global and contemporary technology and are mostly drawn from Latin and French sources. Words in Uzbek are derived from national customs, folk arts, and frequently from the fields of local professions. For instance, the English word "bias" is translated as "diagonal direction" in Uzbek, however this translation is frequently employed in local workmanship. Furthermore, Uzbek is easily translated into English using contemporary technical terms. For instance, the word "overlok" means "overlock" in Uzbek. The phrases used to communicate technical meanings in Uzbek and English also differ noticeably from one another due of the differences in the cultural developments of the two languages nowadays.

- Depending on the specific steps in the process, technical procedures in English are often described using specific terminology:
- Sewing - sewing process.
- Stitching (type or method of stitching).
- Hemming – sewing the edge of clothes.
- Quilting - quilting (stitching with thick material between fabrics).
- Draping is straight sewing or folding of fabric.

In addition, materials and tools occupy the most important place in English and Uzbek craftsmanship. The terms we will discuss now are common in both languages and have their own semantic field. In English: tread - thread, fabric - cloth (in general), cotton - cotton, wool - wool, silk - silk, needle - sewing needle, sewing mashine - sewing machine, bobbin - designed for winding thread device. In Uzbek: thread- ip, fabric - material used for making clothes (mato umumiy ma'noda), cotton - cotton fabric (paxta), wool - fabric made from animal wool (jun), silk - silk fiber or silk fabric (ipak), sewing machine - machine for sewing clothes (tikuv mashinasi).....

Discussion:

The results show that although the terminology of craftsmanship in Uzbek language is mainly adapted to the practice of handicrafts, the terms of handicrafts in English are closely related to modern industry. As English terms are widely used in the context of globalization and technological advancement, we can often use them interchangeably in different languages. Some technical terms in English are not fully translated into Uzbek, that is, they are not translated, or even when translated, they cannot give their full meaning. Expressions and terms in the Uzbek language are more widely used in conversation, and they often express feelings of national identity. In addition, the terms frequently used in English are taken from world technology standards, which indicates that the development of Uzbek terminology does not correspond to technological progress. Some phrases were adopted directly, because some words do not have substitutes for foreign terms in the Uzbek lexicon. Also, the terms widely used in English are based on global technological standards, which showed that the development of terminology in the Uzbek language lags behind technological processes. The lack of suitable alternatives to international terms in Uzbek terminology leads to the direct adoption of some terms.

Conclusion:

At every level of the industry, tailoring words is crucial to effectively representing and advancing skill. These terminologies provide insight into the cultural and artistic dimensions of sewing in addition to elucidating technical procedures.

Among them, conventional terminology and ideas from contemporary technologies are blended, guaranteeing the field's adaptability and the advancement of various degrees.

References:

1. Bo'ronova, M., & Mirzayeva, G. (2022). SPECIFY HOW LEXIS IS GROUPED. *Евразийский журнал социальных наук, философии и культуры*, 2(13), 307-308.
2. "Uzbek terminology" by Hamidulla Dadaboyev, Tashkent, Nodirabegim, 2020 y.
3. Ergashovna, M. G., Xoliqulovna, B. M., & Botirjon ogli, J. V. (2023). TIKUVCHILIKKA OID TERMINLARNING SINONMLARINI TAHLIL QILISH. *Ta'lim innovatsiyasi va integratsiyasi*, 11(2), 44-47.
4. <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/ingliz-va-o-zbek-tillarida-ta-lim-sohasiga-oid-terminlarning-chog-ishtirma-tahlili/viewer>
5. Sobirjonovna, S. M. (2023, December). EXPLAIN EXTENSIVE AND INTENSIVE LISTENING AND PROVIDE EXAMPLES FOR EACH. In *Proceedings of International Conference on Scientific Research in Natural and Social Sciences* (Vol. 2, No. 12, pp. 128-133).
6. <https://uz.wikipedia.org/wiki/Tikuvchilik>
7. Ibodullayevna, S. B., Rajavaliyeva, A. N., G'anievna, A. Q., & Ergashevna, M. G. (2022). John fowles as an existentialist writer and realist literary trends and its philosophical-psychological approaches. *湖南大学学报(自然科学版)*, 49(04).
8. Mirzayeva G.E. Oripova S.N. (2023, March). Analysis of Terms for Sewing in English and Uzbek. *International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*.(pp 377-379)
9. A practical guide to craftsmanship | Creating the craftsmen and women that Britain needs by BILL LUCAS AND ELLEN SPENCER www.cityandguilds.com/apracticalguidetocraftsmanship
10. Сайфуллаев Нажибулло. (2023). ТЕРМИНЫ – НЕОТЪЕМЛЕМОЕ БОГАТСТВО НАШЕГО ЯЗЫКА. *PEDAGOGS*, 46(1), 67–69.